

ASAE's National Sampling Plan

PNCA – Plano Nacional de Colheitas de Amostras

According with Regulation 2017/625¹, Member States must ensure that the official controls and other official activities by the competent authorities of the Member States, are carried out regularly, taking into account the risk categorisation of the official controls.

An ideal control sampling plan, would include all food groups and subgroups available in the food chain. However, and given the impossibility of having the material and monetary resources necessary for this type of control, it became necessary to develop a sampling plan that could represent the population's exposure to risk. For this purpose, the Risk Matrix (RM) was used, which enables the classification of risk groups and, based on this classification the capacity to build a sampling control plan.

The RM has, as inputs, the severity index and the level of occurrence, which combined, characterize the degree of risk and allow a quick identification of the level of risk through its mapping:

- Tool already recognized for risk assessment;
- It allows a qualitative classification;
- It is a tool used by official entities.

		Severity				
		Very Low (1)	Low (2)	Medium (3)	High (4)	Very High (5)
Occurrence (probability)	Certain (5)	Low	Medium	High	High	Extreme
	Likely (4)	Low	Medium	Medium	High	High
	Possible (3)	Low	Medium	Medium	High	High
	Unlikely (2)	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	High
	Rare (1)	Very Low	Low	Low	Medium	High

FIG. 1 – RISK MATRIX

¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products, amending Regulations (EC) No 999/2001, (EC) No 396/2005, (EC) No 1069/2009, (EC) No 1107/2009, (EU) No 1151/2012, (EU) No 652/2014, (EU) 2016/429 and (EU) 2016/2031 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Regulations (EC) No 1/2005 and (EC) No 1099/2009 and Council Directives 98/58/EC, 1999/74/EC, 2007/43/EC, 2008/119/EC and 2008/120/EC, and repealing Regulations (EC) No 854/2004 and (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 89/608/EEC, 89/662/EEC, 90/425/EEC, 91/496/EEC, 96/23/EC, 96/93/EC and 97/78/EC and Council Decision 92/438/EEC (Official Controls Regulation)Text with EEA relevance.

The RM structure allows a qualitative classification of the risk level and its spatial location in the classification grid (colour scale), as shown in fig.1. However, in order to be possible, it is necessary to classify food groups quantitatively according to the level of risk they represent.

For this purpose, we used the Risk Priority Number (RPN) calculation, as a measure indicator of the Failure Mode and Effects Analysis tool (FMEA), to determine the risks.

The RPN details the level of occurrence of the hazards, the level of detection of the hazards and the severity of the consequences of exposure to the hazards, from the consumer's point of view.

$$\text{RPN} = \text{S} \times \text{O} \times \text{D}$$

S = Severity is a numerical estimate of how severe the hazards are, when associated with foodstuffs;

O = Occurrence is the likelihood of the non-compliances from the previous years;

D = Detection is the effectiveness of the controls to prevent or detect the cause

The planning and the methodology adopted evolved from the one used in previous years, with some changes in strategy, among which the introduction of a factor related to consumption habits in Portugal. In collaboration with the Faculty of Nutrition and Food Sciences of the University of Porto (FCNAUP), a planning strategy was defined for The National Sampling Control Plan (PNCA) that included a new variable, namely consumption, obtained from the results of the National Food and Activity Survey Physics (IAN-AF)², implemented between 2014 and 2016 through a consortium involving national and international researchers and whose promoter, was the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto. Thus, in order to include consumption information in the definition of the PNCA, a consumption factor (C) was adopted that focused on the final result of the NPR. It should be noted, therefore, that the IAN-AF assumes itself as an information system to monitor consumption and eating behaviours (including nutritional dimensions, food security and insecurity) in addition to physical activity, that does not contribute to this effect.

To determine the consumption factor, C, the food items reported in the IAN-AF were coded in first place according to the food groups and subgroups considered by ASAE in the PNCA, in order to build a link between these groups and consumption data.

² <https://ian-af.up.pt/>

Then, the average number of servings consumed for each food group/subgroup was estimated from the consumption data of the IAN-AF as an ideal way to represent the consumption factor, C.

$$C = \textit{average n}^{\circ} \textit{ of portions}$$

In this sense, for each reported food item, the respective weighted average portion was defined, in edible grams, taking into account the differential consumption of adults and children. The weighting of the portion size considered a proportion of 20% of children (<10 years) and 80% of adults in the sample, and the average portions considered in adults and children for each food were those defined and used in the IAN-AF.

$$\textit{Weighted average portion} = 0,8 \times \textit{edible portion}_{adults} + 0,2 \times \textit{edible portion}_{children}$$

After defining the weighted portion of each item, the average number of servings consumed daily for each food group/subgroup was determined through the consumption data resulting from the IAN-AF.

$$\textit{average n}^{\circ} \textit{ of portions} = \frac{\textit{Average consumption (g)}}{\textit{Weighted average portion (g)}}$$

The NPR is determined, based on the previous three years of detected non-conformities. After calculating the value of the NPR, the consumption factor was applied to each group of foods, according to the following weighting:

$$P = \frac{2NPR + C}{3}$$

The consumption factor enters with weight 1 and NPR with weight 2. In this way, the calculation of the distribution of samples referring to the safety issues thus gives, weightily, more relevance to the risk, but it takes into account in a decisive way the consumption of GA to sampling, giving rise to a more balanced sampling in the context of the objectives of this official control plan.

Finally, and after the number of samples corresponding to the safety feature (total of 1500 samples) is distributed among the groups, subgroups and foods, the final results are imported into an ACESS database. This database, lists the various tables that will allow the connection of Groups, Subgroups, Foods and Laboratory Determinations with the inherent and applicable determinations for each foodstuff. The final result of the planning for the year 2020 is shown in Fig.2

Group	NPR	$(2NPR+C)/3$	Proportion	Anual sampling n'i
Meat and processed meat	320	407	0,128	191
Fishery products	320	288	0,090	135
Dried fruit	320	229	0,072	108
Dairy products	240	378	0,119	178
Cereals and all products derived from cereals	200	404	0,127	190
Oil and fat	192	253	0,079	119
Fruit and vegetables	168	570	0,179	268
Alcoholic beverages	144	140	0,044	66
Non-alcoholic beverages	120	373	0,117	176
Ready-to-eat foods	40	41	0,013	19
Spices, condiments and sauces	40	46	0,014	21
Sweets and honey	32	39	0,012	18
Eggs and Egg products	24	19	0,006	9
	2160	3186	1	1500

FIG.2 - SAMPLING, STRATEGY VALUES